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Contaminated Air – The Perspective Of a Former Airline-Training Captain

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Abstract

A former airline-training captain reports on contaminated cabin air and its impact on the industry's reputation and pilots' health.

Keywords

cabin air, quality, contamination, medical issue, humility, safety, pilot

We are, currently, living in unprecedented times. Some would say it's the wrong time, to be raising awareness on the issue of contaminated cabin air. Many of our colleagues around the world, fearful of job losses, uncertainty and the ensuing professional and social disruption, caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, would say that there are more immediate and pressing concerns. Of course, these concerns are justified. However, flight safety does not sleep, and if anything, as an industry that prepares for return to work, we as crew members need to be more vigilant and self-aware than ever.

For all who have been affected or yet to be affected by the issue of contaminated cabin air, in looking at the Human Factors, we now need to introduce a little more humanity. We are not machines, and for the poets among you today, I would like to share with you some lines from Rudyard Kipling's wonderful poem, 'The Secret of the Machines' (Kipling 1941). Putting it in context, what follows is from the perspective of the machine as it speaks to the reader:

*But remember, please, the Law by which we live,
We are not built to comprehend a lie,
We can neither love nor pity nor forgive.
If you make a slip in handling us you die,
Be humble, as you crawl beneath our rods.*

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In our industry of late, there has been a distinct lack of this humility, with the many regulatory and manufacturing failures and ensuing loss of life - Hard won reputations established over many decades thrashed in an instant, and for what gain? No effort or endeavour by all should be spared, in restoring what has been lost.

You may indeed ask: "What has any of this got to do with cabin air quality?" to which my reply is: "everything." For it is this very confidence which will be instrumental in restoring our industry's damaged reputation. We are assured by the regulators that 'the air quality on passenger jet aircraft, is similar to, or better than what is observed in normal indoor environments.' Yet, we know that is not the case. It is no longer acceptable to ignore the many recommendations and proposals to install effective monitoring and filtration equipment in aircraft cabins. Those familiar, doubtful refrains of "the science is unclear," or "the data inconclusive," or "more research is required" and "regulation is unjustified," are tiresome and frustrating. Further reading of interest can be found in Professor David Michaels book, 'The Triumph of Doubt' and brings us fresh hope for the future (Michaels 2020).

From those first trial-and-error flights at Kittyhawk, North Carolina, to the highly regulated training environments of today, the advances in these technologies and training were quite unimaginable. This marriage of training and technology has however, not always been a harmonious one. For many years, pilot training was focused on a set of repetitive tasks which had historically contributed to accidents or incidents. The many accidents and incidents that were put down to 'Pilot error' may in fact have had a more sinister cause. Contaminated air was quite simply not a consideration, albeit the industry was aware of a problem from the outset. The question was never asked "why did the pilot make the error?" rather than accepting it as the root cause. Instead of being the end of the investigation, it should in fact have been the start of another. Would the answer have been found in the air that was breathed onboard? Who knows!

We as pilots are a unique occupational group, in terms of the testing and checking that we go through annually, in order to keep our licenses. Often as pilots, our performances will vary from very good to mediocre, and occasionally to bad. In the past, I have seen less than optimal performance, from myself included, put down to tiredness, social or domestic distractions or some other cause. Never was the environment we worked in a consideration.

More worryingly however, is the fact that there may be pilots flying that have medical issues, which they may, or may not be aware of, and not captured at medical renewal. I know pilots who have gone on long term sickness, never to return. Pilots who know they are unwell are afraid to reach out, from fear of the unknown.

In 2006, University College London (UCL) conducted random tests on a group of 27 Airline Pilots. The report found that the tests where these pilots underperformed, mapped perfectly onto the areas they reported subjectively, and in the main showing reduced neurocognitive function. Worryingly, according to the report 'a large proportion of those pilots were still flying at the time.' (Mackenzie Ross 2009).

In 2013, ICAO & IATA produced guidance on evidence-based training - a pilot training concept that is centred around competency-based training principles (IATA 2013). Again, the evidence for this program came from the analysis of accident and incident data, analysed in such a way to identify the competencies a pilot requires to operate an aircraft safely and effectively in today's environments. There are a number of issues with the Learning and Development Sciences and the overload of instructors which are beyond the scope of this brief.

However, I can mention that some legacy issues may create an impediment to experienced pilots being able to change competencies and find a new way to work. Despite the paradigm shift in evidence-based training, it will be of little or no use if it fails to deliver change. Further reading for those interested, is written by Suzanne K. Kearns in her book, 'Competency Based Education in Aviation: Exploring alternative training pathways.' (Kearns 2016).

"Knowing thyself is the key to all wisdom." Be kind to yourself and consider the environment we work in. The time for procrastination has now passed. By working together, the aim is to find a solution and prolong our flying careers. As to whether or not contaminated air is a threat to flight safety, I will let you be the judge of that!

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About the Author

Captain Nicholas McHugh has been a professional pilot for over 40 years. He started his career in the military and has been privileged to fly a variety of aircraft starting with the BAC 1-11, Boeing 737, Boeing 757, Boeing 747 and Airbus A320. He was a training captain on the Boeing 737 and holds a 1st Class Honours Bachelor of Science Degree. He is a board member of the Global Cabin Air Quality Executive (GCAQE).